

Improving English Teaching Methods for Students: A Practical Approach

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Abstract:

In today's interconnected global economy and increasingly multilingual culture, individuals must attain a high level of fluency in the English language in order to be fully competent. Although English has been the primary language in India since the colonial period, it is now acknowledged as a distinct academic field dedicated to the instruction of English.

English language educators are searching for a suitable approach to instruct a significant number of Indian students who have varying language learning capabilities. It is vital for the teachers to comprehend the process and rationale that resulted in their present challenging predicament. They should assess whether the methods are indeed appropriate for their children. Through analyzing previous endeavors, educators can determine the most effective tactics or combinations thereof to achieve the goals of their students, who have various learning styles. The objective of this study is to enlighten the teaching community about the historical transformations in English language teaching methodologies and to evaluate their appropriateness for Indian students. English teachers in India should develop classroom methodologies and strategies that are customized to suit certain circumstances. These tactics and strategies should be based on their theoretical, pedagogical, and empirical knowledge. The objective is to efficiently cater to the unforeseeable requirements, preferences, and situations of individuals learning a second language. This study also investigates teaching methods in the classroom that improve the efficiency of English language training and learning.

This paper seeks to furnish teachers, experts, and professors of second languages with concepts that have the potential to expedite students' mastery of the English language. English, the language of the dominant colonial power in the 17th and 18th centuries and a key factor in the industrial revolution of the 18th and 19th centuries, became the language of global economic and political supremacy in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. With the growth of the global economy and government systems, there was a commensurate rise in global communication, which made it necessary to establish a universal language. English has achieved global prominence as a result of its sophisticated and flexible characteristics. It encourages and simplifies change, accepts emerging societal patterns, teaches fresh knowledge and skills, establishes a structured way of life akin to industrialized countries, and facilitates understanding of global political, social, cultural, and religious problems.

Keywords: English language learning, second language, universe language, language activities, global prominence etc.

Introduction

English is an essential tool for effective communication, allowing individuals in different professional domains to tap into worldwide prospects. English, being the widely used language for business purposes, enables seamless global communication and exchange of information. Every organization values individuals who have the ability to speak multiple languages, especially those who are skilled in English. Devoted individuals to the English language can enjoy a wide range of employment opportunities, advancements in technology and science, economic growth, and an exceptional appreciation for different cultures that is unmatched by any other language. This allows them to effectively communicate with the significant portion of the global population that is fluent in English. In order to thrive in the corporate world, it is crucial to have strong abilities in both verbal and written English. This will boost the probability of being accepted and leave a positive impression of yourself.

The initial development of essential software for communication, information, and study, such as "Windows," "Microsoft Office," "Internet Explorer," and others, is primarily conducted in English. English is the top-ranked language among the five official languages recognized by the United Nations. All research, studies, and information in every field are widely accessible only in the English language. Even without a college education, individuals working in corporations, companies, and organizations demonstrate an impressive command of the English language. A highly skilled employee in English language is more effective in their work compared to others, as they can leverage information from global sources and websites for enhanced preparation. English is widely acknowledged as a prominent language in colleges, which greatly aids students in acquiring knowledge. The English language plays a crucial role in the film and music industries.

Understanding the English language helps in grasping the culture, customs, and societal norms in both English-speaking countries and non-English-speaking countries. English is widely recognized as the primary language for global communication, making it the most effective tool for scholars, diplomats, politicians, and scientists to engage in discussions, negotiations, and collaborations. In order to thrive in life, it is crucial to develop a strong command of the English language. English is widely studied by individuals from different countries as a second language. It acts as the main method of communication for people who speak different native

languages on a daily basis. English has had a profound impact on human history, thanks to its extensive use over many centuries and its position as the dominant language of powerful nations and influential individuals. It has become a fundamental element in the stories of many cultures, like a cultural seed.

Indian English

In the past, English served as a means of communication between the rulers and the subjects. It played a significant role in India's national existence. During the period of the freedom movement, educated Indians transformed their perspectives, thereby influencing the perspectives of ordinary Indians and motivating their active participation in the war for independence. Consequently, this resulted in the attainment of the nation's autonomy. In post-independence India, it became an integral component of daily existence that was irremovable. Despite not being an indigenous language of India, English is currently utilized to the same extent as any other language. It is adopted as the official language predominantly utilized by office professionals and individuals with higher education to communicate with one another. Additionally, it serves as the primary means of communication for governments, courts, legislatures, science, technology, education, progress, jobs, industry, and trade, and is seen as a symbol of personal growth, among other purposes. It continues to exert a significant influence on the lives and careers of the majority of educated Indians across all sectors. English language instruction has significantly evolved since the concept of freedom was introduced. It has been incorporated into the educational curriculum of schools and institutions as a second language.

English is a mandatory subject for every second-grade student, and it is taught at all educational levels. It is an obligatory subject in educational institutions, ranging from schools to universities, and serves as the primary method of instruction for most courses. Teaching English as a second language has emerged as a significant discipline within our educational curriculum.

Teaching English presents a notable challenge, but there is an increasing recognition among children, parents, the general public, and even politicians regarding this issue. Acquiring the language can be quite challenging for many Indian children. On the other hand, educators put in a lot of work to figure out the best ways to help children learn English. Usually, when English instructors teach a foreign language, they either give an explanation of its meaning or translate

the English text into the native language. This instructional approach enhances the learner's understanding of the text. Unfortunately, the learners struggle to completely separate themselves from their native language, which hinders their ability to gain proficiency in the target language and leaves them feeling uncertain about their English skills.

Students feel at ease with a language they have effortlessly acquired during their upbringing, which gives them a sense of comfort. In a multilingual environment, finding a middle ground between using local languages and a common language can be quite a task. The main focus in English language instruction should be on the practical application of the language in everyday conversations. Furthermore, it is essential to educate individuals on the structure of communication and the abilities required to construct and produce grammatically correct, meaningful, purposeful, and contextually suitable sentences. English is taught in a scholarly manner, rather than being incorporated into a course that emphasizes practical skills.

According to Allen Corder (1973), language can be viewed as a form of knowledge, and the process of learning it can be likened to studying subjects such as chemistry. If an action is marked by expertise, it will be developed through consistent practice. If an object is present, we can gain knowledge about it through detailed descriptions or by fully utilizing it. In social situations, we will be inclined to actively participate in the social interactions that occur. The user's response is lacking in detail and does not offer any substantial information. As educators of the English language, they must understand their role in facilitating the acquisition of language proficiency in students. Once individuals acquire those talents, they will be capable of managing any topic or circumstance.

According to Allen and Corder (1973), language teachers are not primarily instructors of language, but rather those who demonstrate to their students both novel and familiar methods of utilizing the language they already possess. (68) This highlights the importance of educators in discovering the untapped potential of their students by fostering their confidence. Teachers should design activities that engage students in enjoyable language exercises, helping them develop their skills and grasp the intricacies of language. In order to accomplish this, educators must gain an understanding of the essential elements of the language in order to grasp how it operates. Without this, it will be difficult for children to find any hope or solution when it comes to teaching language-related matters.

The teacher's role is to guide students in using their language skills, without focusing on the technical aspects of the language. When a teacher elucidates the significance of a written item, they are providing instruction on the subject of language. On the other hand, a teacher can effectively educate students on how to use a language as a practical tool by offering instruction on its usage and ample opportunities for practice. Afterwards, the teacher will share information about the language itself. The children can learn and understand the language with the guidance of the teacher. It is essential for every educator to ensure that every classroom equips children with the necessary language skills.

Proficiency in various linguistic skills is crucial for effectively conveying ideas, emotions, preferences, information, and other forms of communication. The objective of English instruction in India is to motivate students to engage in the study of the language by increasing their awareness of its importance. Hence, the principal objective should be to instruct a student to depend on their abilities. The proverb "If you give a man a fish, you feed him for a day, but if you teach a man to fish, you feed him for a lifetime" is highly accurate. The educator's responsibility is to persuade the student that achieving mastery in English is essential for their future success in a globalized setting.

Strategies for the Instruction of a Second Language:

The pedagogies for teaching foreign or second languages have undergone significant changes over the 20th and 21st centuries. It is crucial to assess if the commonly employed methods effectively facilitate or impede language acquisition in the classroom. New instructional approaches will be identified to improve organizational skills, promote knowledge retention, and facilitate communication.

Cummins (1979) discovered that a student's ability to use a language is influenced by their competency in their first language. This conclusion was reached after examining challenges related to learning English as a second language and attending bilingual education programs. In the 1980s, researchers started postulating that students possess diverse learning styles, which requires educators to utilize a broad array of educational approaches. Dunn & Dunn were the first to introduce the utilization of many senses in the educational setting. In their study, Guild and Garger (1985) identified a range of factors that have an impact on education. They concluded that the auditory, visual, and kinesthetic modalities are the most efficient methods

for transmitting knowledge. In 1983, Gardner identified seven distinct brain regions that are associated with different types of intelligence. Later, he identified an additional eighth region. His groundbreaking views proposed that individuals possess various methods of cognitive processing and that students will gain advantages from receiving personalized instruction that aligns with their unique intelligence.

According to Sparks's (2006) study, students with different learning styles can achieve success in language sessions, particularly those that emphasize second languages, when provided with appropriate stimuli and assessments. Foreign and second language teachers might get advantages by studying the evolution of different instructional methods through exploring the historical background of language education.

The major objective of the Grammar Translation Method in the 20th century was to commit verb paradigms, grammar rules, and vocabulary to memory. The tasks consist of translating sentences from the target language to the source language, and vice versa. A small amount of time is dedicated to the practice of pronunciation. (Mora, 2002). During the 1990s, as communicative approaches became more prominent, many educators held a negative view towards them. Nevertheless, some elements of this technique have been essential to Foreign Language Teaching and remain pertinent in the present. The Reading Method closely resembled the conventional Grammar/Translation technique, with its main emphasis on literal translations of literary texts. The exclusive criterion for teaching grammar was reading comprehension. Insufficient attention was devoted to the development of pronunciation and conversational abilities during the course. (Kennedy 2002).

The imperative to instruct military personnel in the art of speaking fast and convincingly emerged during and following World War II. The program included activities such as memorizing dialogues, practising listening and speaking skills, and working on pronunciation. Instructors were permitted to communicate in their native languages, whereas students were strongly advised against doing so. The Direct Method required that all classes be conducted solely in the target language, placing a strong focus on oral communication and eliminating the use of a translator. Teachers would orally provide a narrative in the desired language and thereafter inquire students about the narrative through a sequence of questions. Another

prominent full immersion technique that has persisted since the 1960s is known as "Content-Based Instruction," and it is extensively utilized in bilingual elementary schools.

The "Feel-Good" movement of the 1970s emphasized the need for a nurturing school environment and educators who demonstrate real concern for their students. The strategies facilitated more authentic dialogue in ordinary contexts. The underlying principle of The Silent Way was that the absence of verbal input from the teacher would motivate students to produce a maximum amount of authentic language. (Bowen 2007)

The utilization of concrete examples to elucidate concepts is now universally acknowledged as a fundamental element of this method. The significance of problem-solving skills in conversation was also emphasized. Students were motivated to assume control over their language learning experiences through the utilization of the Community Language Learning Method, wherein the instructor acted as a source of encouragement and guidance. This technique introduced the concept that the attitude of teachers and the characteristics of the classroom environment had a substantial impact on student performance.

Krashen popularized the Natural Communication or whole language Approach, which is based on the premise that students may acquire a language only via exposure to and comprehension of written and spoken material in the target language. Students similarly acquire a new language to a kid, through the process of listening to and mimicking native speakers. Students imitate the teacher's facial expressions and eventually employ the language to express their thoughts, emotions, attitudes, and requests. Students participate in unstructured pair and group conversation exercises. Teachers should initially assume the role of facilitators, then monitor their students' progress, and ultimately provide constructive feedback on how they might enhance their language skills (Bowen, 2007; Kennedy, 2007).

A significant number of foreign language teachers discontinued the use of Direct techniques following the rise in popularity of Krashen's book. Teachers are obligated to embrace communicative methods according to the National Standards for Foreign Language Learning (2007). His proponents contend that his approach is preferable to conventional grammar instruction as it enables children to acquire the language naturally. The function evolved throughout this linguistic turmoil. The text highlights five distinct categories of language usage: intrapersonal, interpersonal, directive, referential, and creative. These categories are intended

to enhance and promote effective communication (Finocchiaro, 1983). The principles of the Communicative Approach were further developed in the Lexical Approach, which prioritizes teaching language in meaningful contexts rather than as a collection of unrelated words. The concept of differentiated education was initially introduced by Dunn and Dunn in 1978. Over the years, educators have devised methods that accommodate students' unique learning preferences, including their different intelligences, learning styles, and sensory preferences.

The notion of Total Physical Response (TPR) started to emerge in the 1990s. The concept is based on the notion that connecting activity with memory enhances the ability to remember. The Natural Approach to teaching foreign languages to both adults and children relies on physical reactions to commands such as "pick it up" and "put it down". (Bowen, 2007)

The Nine Intelligences Hypothesis, proposed by Gardener in 1983 and 1993, serves as the basis for the Multiple Intelligences Approach. Students with different cognitive abilities can comprehend the same content by structuring each class session around a core concept and engaging all students in a variety of interconnected games and activities. The concept of project-based learning is that when students engage in extensive research on real-world topics and pertinent scenarios, they develop a more profound comprehension of the significance of FL. Since the beginning of the 21st century, teaching practices in foreign language education have focused on integrating many ways to stimulate students' utilization of various senses, intelligences, and technologies in the classroom.

In Task-Based Education, learners are encouraged to utilize the language they are most at ease with while they engage in activities that simulate real-life situations or experiences. The Total Response Storytelling Method use concise and amusing narratives to establish and enhance a system of manual gestures that the teacher utters. The instructor iterates the narrative on many occasions, elaborating on the specifics with each repetition. Students initially cooperate with a partner to retell the narrative before independently creating their versions. The Focus-on-Form Approach aims to close the divide between conventional grammatical teaching and the acquisition of conversational language skills. The inter-hemispheric foreign language learning approach is based on scientific research on the human brain. It employs rhythmic oration and complete bodily relaxation.

Florida instructors are beginning to develop lesson plans that necessitate students to engage both hemispheres of the brain. There has been considerable debate on the most effective methodology for teaching foreign languages, although no consensus has been reached. While communication exercises may be popular, there is little scientific evidence to support their superior effectiveness compared to alternative ways. Multiple studies have shown that using a combination of senses and a straightforward method is crucial when teaching the relationship between sounds, symbols, and grammar to second language learners. Several research conducted on animals demonstrate that teachers can exert an influence on brain development. Skills should not be taught in isolation as learning can progress both from simple to complex and from complicated to simple.

Students need sufficient time and repeated practice to solidify recently learned skills and information. Foreign language teachers can enhance their ability to generate a wide range of ideas that are relevant to the specific context while being consistent with current pedagogical and theoretical knowledge. This enables them to effectively address the various and unpredictable needs, desires, and situations of both second language teachers and students. The correlation between theoretical ideas and classroom approaches enhances the effectiveness of second language training. If teachers understand this connection, they will be able to create comprehensive principles that may be used as a blueprint for their classroom activities. The general designs of these methodologies for second language instruction and learning are based on theoretical, empirical, and pedagogical information.

There is a widespread belief that teaching a language is impossible, although it is feasible to establish circumstances that facilitate its development in the mind, according to its unique process. Classroom instruction is exclusively based on an interactive approach that creates learning possibilities. Teaching is predominantly seen as a process that creates chances for learning, whereas learning is seen as a process that takes advantage of those chances. Both teachers and students can generate and utilize educational opportunities.

The instructional activity's ability to create and take advantage of learning opportunities is primarily influenced by the teaching styles of instructors and the learning methods of students. For example, the lecturer will request discussion ideas from her students. After gathering multiple subjects, she introduced her own. Upon receiving a student's inquiry for a term's

definition, she does not provide a quick response. Instead, she asks that people clarify. Even after a student has given a satisfactory answer, the teacher checks with the other students to make sure that everyone has understood the subject. Proficient students in communication are obligated to peruse an essay on a designated subject, while the teacher fosters engagement and participation by facilitating engaging class discussions.

Both teachers and students are considered learners as they actively contribute to the creation of instructional discourse and the administration of learning. The teacher, possessing both competence and authority, actively participates in a collaborative endeavour to implement educational instruction. Regardless of whether the student's speech is directly relevant to the current activity, the instructor must make use of the learning possibilities presented by the student. Rather than dismissing the learner's inaccurate response or merely categorizing it as wrong, the teacher should transcribe it on the board and utilize it as a teaching moment.

The instructor is responsible for promoting meaningful contact among students by ensuring that they actively participate in activities such as seeking clarification, checking comprehension, confirming understanding, repairing communication breakdowns, reacting to others, and taking turns. Additionally, students should be encouraged to use communication tactics like circumlocution (describing something indirectly) and paraphrasing (expressing something in different words). Various empirical studies have shown the importance of negotiated engagement. Long's research has shown that when the input and interaction in second language learning are adjusted, it improves comprehension and leads to the development of the language. Swain (39) showed that when learners are compelled to control the existing interlanguage system, they gain the chance to enhance their ability to produce language in the second language. Within this type of class, the lecturer and the students work together to create relevant discussions in the classroom.

Language Related Activities for Learners

The teacher's questions are intended to prompt the students to share their ideas on the issue being addressed, rather than gathering language examples that may be mechanically taken from the textbook or remembered from memory. In a classroom where there is limited opportunity for interactive discussion, the professors will typically provide the answers to their questions or stop asking questions once a brilliant student has given the first correct response. The

activities include listening exercises, dialogues, reading and storytelling, debates, problem-solving, creating functional situations, illustrating concepts, reading/creating maps, interpreting directions, mind mapping, acting out an event, paired conversation, surveys and polls, team problem-solving, group brainstorming, peer teaching, partner or mentor interviews, goal setting, and self-monitoring. The following steps can be undertaken by the teacher in a language classroom:

- Students receive instruction in language concepts in a systematic manner and are supported in categorizing and arranging these concepts in order of increasing difficulty.
- Build upon students' existing knowledge and establish the connection between their prior knowledge and the new material.
- Instruct systematically and explicitly on the phonemes or speech sounds of the foreign language. Instruct students on the phonetics of the letters in the foreign language and their corresponding meanings.

Over the 20th and 21st centuries, there have been significant advancements in the methods used to teach foreign languages. Foreign language teachers have evolved from using direct grammar instruction and translation to exclusively teaching in the target language. They have also adopted holistic methods that involve the body, mind, and spirit, as well as emphasizing communication for community use. Furthermore, they have started to tailor their instruction to accommodate variations in intelligence, modality preferences, and learning styles. Instructors are currently being encouraged by both public and private enterprises to utilize a combination of tactics, including the "natural" approach, multisensory education, technology, projects, and communicative activities.

Although educators have time constraints and are unable to handle linguistic components. Nevertheless, the teacher can allocate a minimum of 10 minutes per class to educate students on language components, while the rest of the time can be utilized for traditional instruction. Supervision from a language instructor is crucial for children to master a language. Every second language teacher should instruct each class to provide students with the essential language skills they need.

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